

ELIXIR

Cellular & Molecular Research - Strategy

Unifying Cellular and Molecular Research through Integrated Data

About this document

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Abstract

The Cellular and Molecular Research (CMR) Strategy sets out ELIXIR's roadmap for accelerating scientific discovery by streamlining data integration and fostering multi-modal and multi-omics research across Europe. By unifying data silos, promoting standards, and supporting FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, this strategy aims to address the core challenges of connecting diverse datasets, methods, and communities. Emphasising close collaborations — with both emerging and established research infrastructures — CMR provides a platform for sharing computational tools and developing advanced workflows, particularly in AI and machine learning. The strategy's implementation relies on targeted funding via open calls, capacity-building through cross-Node training, and the alignment of key stakeholder groups, ensuring that best practices for data management and analytics are embedded throughout ELIXIR Communities. Ultimately, the CMR Strategy aspires to transform cellular and molecular research into a highly coordinated ecosystem, unlocking new insights and enabling faster, more efficient innovations in life science research.

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Introduction

Background

The Cellular and Molecular Research (CMR) Scientific Priority Area is a key component of ELIXIR's research infrastructure strategy. It aims to address the complex challenges in cellular and molecular research by developing innovative solutions for data management, analysis, and sharing. This document outlines the structured strategy for CMR, including its challenges, vision, mission, objectives and implementation.

Challenges

The main challenges in CMR revolve around the high levels of data integration, standardisation, and community collaboration needed for multimodal studies and analyses. In particular, linking diverse datasets is a persistent problem, whether across studies, repositories, or data types like multi-omics, imaging, and phenotypes. As repeated analysis of the growing quantity of raw biological data becomes less efficient and more impractical, the level of integration is also shifting towards comparing and combining summarised data as well as generating machine learning models. This represents an even greater hurdle and can only be solved through improved FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) of data and AI models, with rich metadata and consolidation of standards across different communities, particularly for non-model organisms. Barriers also exist in the practicalities of such research, including managing sensitive data, integrating time-course datasets, the complexities of systems biology, and supporting emerging data types - as aspects of multimodality. Lastly, promoting effective collaboration and coherence among cellular and molecular researchers is a key challenge both within ELIXIR and across the global research community.

Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats

Strengths

- Strong interdisciplinary connections within ELIXIR Communities and beyond, facilitating effective collaboration.
- Proven expertise in computer science, biology, data management, bioinformatics analysis, and development of established standards.
- Existing infrastructure with established databases, analytical tools, and ongoing service provision that can be scaled and enhanced through targeted and strategic investment.

Weaknesses

- Uneven engagement levels across Communities, with some lacking direct involvement in data production or analysis.
- Incomplete representation of specific cellular and molecular subdomains within current ELIXIR Community structures.
- Limited availability of funding streams, constraining sustained strategic development and infrastructure maintenance.
- Variability and complexity in biological protocols, affecting reproducibility, traceability, and interoperability.

Opportunities

- Expansion through integration of new ELIXIR Nodes, enhancing geographic and thematic coverage across Europe.
- Targeted outreach and effective showcasing of services to attract new Community members and stakeholders.
- Promotion and adoption of federated, standardised data repositories tailored to diverse data types.
- Facilitate the implementation of multimodal research services by supporting interoperability and seamless integration across repositories.
- Collaboration or leadership in European Commission-funded initiatives, amplifying visibility and resource-sharing with peer Research Infrastructures.

Threats

- Emergence of competitor initiatives providing similar or overlapping services, potentially diluting community engagement.
- Challenges in sustaining technical currency and relevance once project-specific funding ends.
- Rapid technological advancements demanding continuous upgrades and content management, creating potential maintenance burdens.
- Intensifying competition for limited project funding opportunities at national and European levels.

Aims

Vision

The Cellular and Molecular Research Priority Area of ELIXIR envisions a future where data silos are unified. Today, valuable research data resides in isolated repositories, often limited to a single experimental method or a single technology. This fragmented landscape hinders the power of multi-omics and multi-modal analyses, the cornerstone of modern research.

We believe the present and future of cellular and molecular research lies in integrating diverse, heterogeneous and multi-modal data – from sequence-based data such as genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and more, to structural information, image data and beyond – to unravel the complex mechanisms of life.

The Cellular and Molecular Research Priority Area of the ELIXIR Science Tier enables a foundational data infrastructure that underpins the research efforts of specific Communities:

- Communities, such as 3D Bioinformatics, Single-Cell Omics and Systems Biology, require the integration of diverse data types to understand complex biological systems. The focus on multi-omics analysis empowers them to analyse and interpret their data within a holistic cellular and molecular context.
- Communities, such as Intrinsically Disordered Proteins, Metabolomics, Microbial Biotechnology and Proteomics, all rely on high-throughput data generation techniques. Commitment to data standardisation and interoperability ensures their data can be effectively integrated and compared with data from other areas of cellular and molecular research.

Mission

To accelerate scientific progress in cellular and molecular research by fostering a robust data infrastructure and strengthening collaborations across Europe.

1. Foster Strategic Collaborations:

- Establish productive partnerships with other European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructure (ESFRI) organisations, prioritising Instruct-ERIC and Euro BioImaging.
- Collaborate with relevant cellular and molecular societies and organisations (e.g., Federation of European Biochemical Societies (FEBS), European Molecular Biology Organisation (EMBO), International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB)) to promote ELIXIR, its Platforms and Communities.

2. Advocate for Foundational Research:

- Lobby for increased funding and visibility of foundational cellular and molecular research at the European level.

3. Standardisation and Data Stewardship:

- Coordinate and support the development of community-driven standards for data management and exchange, taking successes like MIADE¹ (IDP Community²) and DOME recommendations³ (Machine Learning Focus Group⁴) as examples.
- Prioritise solutions for the "long tail" of cellular and molecular data – data not readily accommodated by existing databases – by creating a framework for establishing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) databases from inception.

4. Connecting Technologies and Users:

- Bridge the gap between ELIXIR's technological advancements and the needs of diverse cellular and molecular research communities.
- Encourage a feedback loop between communities and developers to guide further technological development, especially in the new and emerging AI ecosystem.

5. Emerging Opportunities:

- Proactively identify emerging scientific areas and opportunities that require new infrastructure, databases, or connections within and beyond ELIXIR.
- Harness the momentum of proven successes, such as AlphaFold, to support and consolidate machine learning services, tools, and standards into a cohesive ecosystem of AI solutions that can be readily adapted and applied to diverse large-scale molecular data.

¹ Mészáros, B., Hatos, A., Palopoli, N. *et al.* 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-023-01915-x>

² <https://elixir-europe.org/communities/intrinsically-disordered-proteins>

³ Walsh, Ian, *et al.* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01205-4>

⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/focus-groups/machine-learning>

6. Community Support and Training:

- Provide impartial oversight and strategic support to ELIXIR Communities working in the CMR field, ensuring their continued success and growth.
- Facilitate training and knowledge exchange on data management, analysis tools, workflows, resources, and engagement with relevant CMR projects.

Goals

Objectives

The CMR Priority Area is set to achieve the vision of unifying Cellular and Molecular Research through integrated data via a set of key objectives:

- Capture the Full Analytical Journey: Moving beyond the data management challenges and solutions, we will aim to capture researchers' analytical strategies and workflows that closely complement and build on multi-modal data. This will enable researchers to not only access data, but also understand how it was generated and analysed, facilitating reuse and accelerating discovery.
- Foster Interoperability, Access and Collaboration in Data: Relying on the robust data standards and resources provided by the wider ELIXIR community, as well as the respective tools and services, we will support and facilitate the development of solutions that seamlessly integrate multimodal data across different platforms and institutions. This will foster a collaborative environment where researchers can leverage the collective power of multimodal analysis.
- Empower Researchers: Capacity building across Nodes is a key priority in CMR. As such we will ensure that the community members across Nodes will have access to training resources, empowering researchers of all levels to navigate and utilise the integrated data landscape. Moreover, we aim to support active involvement in competitive project proposals at a European level.
- Paving the way for AI: Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) have emerged as a key technology with a clear impact in Cellular and Molecular Research. We will directly support trustworthy and FAIR ML in ELIXIR, by supporting the development of services and infrastructure to access, deposit, share and re-use ML models across the wider community.

Expected Impacts and Outcomes

The Priority Area will have a broad impact across several key areas. Some examples are listed below:

- Engagement of researchers in cellular and molecular research within ELIXIR Nodes
- Enhanced Node interactions, coordination, and cooperation in the development and delivery of tools and services
- Cross-Community interactions and development of horizontally aligned standards within the CMR umbrella

- ELIXIR recognised as a valued partner by other research infrastructure initiatives and projects in the cellular and molecular domain, including:
 - Collaboration with Instruct-ERIC on FAIR data principles and tools for structural biology data
 - Partnership with EuroBioImaging to integrate imaging data and services with molecular datasets
- Development of exemplar datasets, use cases, and success stories demonstrating ELIXIR services that evolve into widely adopted solutions
- Adoption of ELIXIR services beyond ELIXIR Nodes, extending to European and international research communities
- Improved flow of information and expertise from field specialists on cellular and molecular data analysis to stakeholders, facilitating informed decision-making

Implementation

As part of the ELIXIR 2024–2026 work programme, several instruments are in place to support the development and growth of the CMR Priority Area. The implementation plan prioritises a strategic approach to funding emphasising collaboration. In addition to the strategic commitment of establishing CMR as a Priority Area and providing funding for its leadership, the following concrete instruments are available:

Workshops and Collaborative Events

Encouraging ELIXIR-wide engagement and input will help develop CMR as a Priority Area and improve its integration and hence impact on the broader ELIXIR landscape:

- **In-person workshops** – Organised as part of other events, such as the ELIXIR All Hands meetings, they will facilitate strategic discussions and the dissemination of ongoing CMR activities across Nodes and Platforms.
- **Cross-Community meetings** – Regular meetings support alignment of CMR related activities across Communities and allow ELIXIR members to refine priorities and identify emerging opportunities within the CMR domain.

Open Calls

Open calls aim to fund projects that align with the mission, vision, and key objectives of the CMR Priority Area. These calls will support both bottom-up proposals from across ELIXIR Nodes and strategically defined projects initiated or guided by the Priority Area co-leads. While funded project members will be the key drivers of these activities, all ELIXIR members are encouraged to contribute, representing their respective Nodes. Potential project areas include:

- **Strategically important, emerging Communities** – Supporting the formation and growth of new Communities aligned with ELIXIR's strategic goals.
- **Consolidating existing ELIXIR Communities** – Strengthening the impact and cohesion of established Communities.
- **Cross-Community collaboration** – Facilitating joint activities such as workshops, hackathons, and development projects that enhance cooperation between Communities.

European Funding Partnerships

ELIXIR can also advance these themes through targeted partnerships in Horizon Europe (HE) and other European Commission funded projects. This involves mapping out the various Horizon Europe (HE) and Cluster Specific calls over the next few years, and proactively identifying potential consortia for engagement, such as Instruct-ERIC and EuroBioImaging. Particular arrangements include:

- **Hub-coordinated projects** – The ELIXIR Hub can coordinate 2–3 pan-European proposals each year, focusing on areas such as Research Infrastructure Consolidation or the development of the European Open Science Cloud.
- **Node-coordinated projects** – When funding is available for specific scientific or technology themes, individual ELIXIR Nodes with domain expertise can lead proposals on behalf of ELIXIR.
- **Member participation in EC-funded projects** – ELIXIR members can also participate in EC-funded projects as part of broader consortia.

Strategy ownership

This strategy is jointly owned by the Cellular and Molecular Research Priority co-leads, who will consolidate feedback from ELIXIR Communities, ensuring that diverse perspectives are reflected in the strategy. This approach ensures that a broad range of stakeholders can provide input throughout the review process, maintaining shared accountability and alignment with the overarching objectives of the ELIXIR Scientific Programme.

Further Reading

Multi-Omics and Multi-Modal Data Integration

AI-readiness for Biomedical Data: Bridge2AI Recommendations – <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.10.23.619844>

Multimodal Biomedical AI – <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01981-2>

Machine Learning Pipelines: Provenance, Reproducibility and FAIR Data Principles – https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80960-7_17

Machine Learning and AI in Molecular Research

DLHub: Model and Data Serving for Science – <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPS.2019.00038>

Successful and Timely Uptake of Artificial Intelligence in Science in the EU – <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/46863>

FAIR Data Principles and Data Infrastructure

FAIR for Machine Learning Model, Principles and Assessment Metrics – <https://zenodo.org/records/13835105>

Cost of Not Having FAIR Research Data – <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/02999>

FAIR AI Models in High Energy Physics – <https://doi.org/10.1088/2632-2153/ad12e3>

FUTURE-AI: international consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable artificial intelligence in healthcare – <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-081554>

FAIR for AI: An Interdisciplinary and International Community Building Perspective – <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02298-6>

Understanding the Role of FAIR for Machine Learning – <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006429415>

HPCFAIR: Enabling FAIR AI for HPC Applications – <https://doi.org/10.1109/MLHPC54614.2021.00011>